

Organic and natural nutrient-based pulse production in drylands of India : A Review

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Abstract

Pulses are one of the most self-sustainable crop plants which act as an important protein source in vegetarian diet. Pulses are mostly grown in drylands of India wherein marginal soils are not suitable for intensive chemical farming-based practices. These soils are well suitable for low input farming practices such as organic agriculture wherein soil flora plays an important role on sustaining soil ecological systems. Pulses with their high biomass production and nodulation capacity add up a lot of nutrients and organic matter to such soils and help in making soils as a vital living system. Pulses with their root nodulation fix atmospheric nitrogen and add up a large amount of nitrogen to soil as well as in their own biomass. Organic agriculture-based inputs such as farm yard manure, vermicompost, farm compost, vermiwash and biofertilizers are well known to enhance organic carbon content levels that are well known to enhance soil microbial population and their activity in recycling of soil nutrients. Organic matter is a major source of nitrogen and sulphur which are the important nutrient elements for improving yield and quality of pulses with respect to grain yield levels and protein content in pulses. Integrated use of pulses and organic nutrient sources can boost up soil biological, chemical and physical properties and thus, growing of pulses using organic nutrient sources seems to be the need of the hour to improve the soil health in drylands and maintain pulse productivity.

Climatic Risk Analysis for Water Availability to Crops in Three Selected Districts of Zone IIIA of Bihar

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Abstract

Rainfed agro-ecosystem plays an important role in Indian agriculture. Fulfilling water demand of crops is one important aspect for achieving potential productivity under rainfed condition. As several risks are involved in rainfed agriculture, it is necessary to slice down the climatic risks for achieving sustainable production. Hence, correct evaluation of water availability and also water stress during different phenological stages of crops is an important pre-requisite for crop planning under rainfed condition. Keeping all this in view, an agroclimatic study was conducted for three districts of Agroclimatic Zone IIIA of Bihar viz. Bhagalpur, Banka and Jamui to evaluate the climatic